

Understanding Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs): Students, Tutors, and Providers

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Introduction

In the digital era, the Internet has become a chief source of knowledge and a tool for learning (Porter, 2014; Hajeer, 2020). Computers (Beatty, 2010), mobile devices (Zhang, 2012) and their various programs, platforms, and applications can offer an entrance into the boundless world of information, giving access to knowledge which has offered access to learning for people around the world (Weis, Benmayor, O’Leary, & Eynon, 2002). A recent development in this democratization of learning has been the emergence of MOOCs. MOOCs are considered as a tool to facilitate access to higher education for large numbers of people interested (Patru & Venkataraman, 2016). Entities which act as MOOC providers can be divided into non-profit colleges and universities such as Stanford, Yale, and Harvard, and for-profit MOOCs providers such as Coursera, Udacity, and Udemy (Rhoades, 2015).

Hoy (2014) defines MOOCs as “a group of online classes that share several key features. The most obvious is that all content is delivered online, either through video, slideshows, discussion boards, or any combination thereof. Courses are usually developed by well-known figures in the field from large research institutions, but in reality, anyone can create a MOOC” (Hoy, 2014, p. 86).

Additionally, most of these online courses have online debate groups where tens of thousands of students (or tutors) may share their experiences as well as their opinions regarding a course that they have taken or are currently attending (Hoy, 2014). This study is based on Hoy’s (2014) definition of MOOCs as this definition may be argued to be the most inclusive since it addresses the channel and mode of delivery in addition to the instructors of MOOCs.

The current theoretical investigation aims to provide an overview of the literature regarding the history of MOOCs, the students who enroll in MOOCs, the tutors who teach MOOCs and the platforms that provide MOOCs to help gain deeper understanding of this phenomenon. Therefore, the present literature review comprises five subsections. The first one provides information about the history of MOOCs. The second subsection presents information about the students who typically join MOOCs such as their age, their educational background, and their country of origin. The third section turns towards the various types of MOOC instructors and discusses the studies that addressed what motivates MOOC tutors to launch such courses and the challenges they encounter when they design them. Fourth, details regarding the platforms that provide MOOCs are presented. Finally, a summary of the main points of the overview is provided.

A Historical Overview

From a historical point of view, Hodges (2008) alleges that email-based courses marked the beginning of open online learning. Wiley and Gurrel (2009), however, postulate that the web-based courses, where enrollees can schedule their own studying time, started as soon as the world wide web was open for the public. That is, open education resources and open learning preceded the rise of MOOCs (Stracke, Downes, Conole, Burgos, & Nascimbeni, 2019). The first MOOC

was introduced in 2008 by Stephen Downes and George Siemens at the University of Manitoba on the topic of Connectivism Learning Theory. In the beginning, about 25 students took the MOOC for credits, but later around 2,300 students enrolled in the course to learn about the taught topic, which can be considered a great success for the first MOOC (Rhodes, 2015). Afterwards, the number of MOOCs, and the number of MOOC students started to increase rapidly due to the huge media campaigns (Rhodes, 2015). One MOOC platform (edSurge) reported that 1,200 MOOCs were offered on this platform from more than 200 universities and taken by over 10 million students (Rhodes, 2015). Later, many modified versions of MOOCs were introduced, which were argued to have met the needs of various kinds of audiences (Stracke, et al., 2019). An example may be of Small Private Online Courses (SPOC), which alleges to provide more interpersonal connection with the students (Guo, 2017).

The first MOOC that was introduced by Stephen Downes and George Siemens did not concentrate on the content of the course per se; instead, the emphasis was on the idea of establishing networks and sharing resources across these networks (Stracke, et al., 2019). The idea of this MOOC was guided by the Connectivist Learning Theory by Siemens (2004). This theory suggests that the world consists of a group of networks where social and physical issues can be solved through the cooperation of collaborating individuals (i.e., group work) (Rhodes, 2015). The type of MOOC that follows the connectivist pedagogy was labeled as ‘cMOOC’, where ‘c’ stands for connectivist. Another type of MOOCs, called ‘xMOOC’ (where x stands for eXtended) came into the scene in 2011, which is a type of MOOC that is concerned with providing educational content to a wide public audience (Stracke, et al., 2019).

Many scholars were excited about MOOCs and considered them as potential tools to revolutionize higher education forever by making it available for large numbers of students (Selingo, 2012). Others, however, were concerned whether MOOCs are indeed capable of replacing conventional classroom education (Toven & Lendsey, 2013). Altbach (2013), nonetheless, had a different perspective as he regarded MOOCs as a new means for the western academia to dominate higher education in the rest of the world by making it accessible to everyone. Despite the various attitudes towards MOOCs, it is extremely difficult to deny the fact that the MOOC movement has influenced higher education (Rhodes, 2015).

Trend of Enrollment

Jordan (2014:153) researched the trends of enrollment and completion of MOOCs, focusing on the platforms Edx, Udacity, and Coursera due to their media attention and the author’s claim that they reflect the higher education sector. The author gathered data from 88 courses and found that the number of enrolled students ranged between 4,500 and 226,652, with a median value of 42,844. The rate of students who completed the course, in other words, the students who gained completion certificates for the courses, ranged from 0.9% to 36.1%, with a median value of 6.5% (Jordan, 2017, p. 147). These relatively low completion rates have also been reflected in other studies on MOOCs, such as the one by Pursel, Zhang, Jablowkow, Choi and Velegol (2016).

Research on the students’ dropout reasons suggests four factors responsible for the high dropout rates, namely, personal, social, academic and course-related factors (Aldowah, Al-Samarraie, Alzahrani, & Alalwan, 2020). Incompetent online skills (Khalil & Ebner, 2014), the lack of previous experience concerning MOOCs (Yamba-Yugsi & Lujan Mora, 2017) can be considered as personal reasons for dropout. Social factors are for instance limited social interaction with other students, the instructor or the content that discourage students from completing the MOOC they enrolled in (Whitehill, Mohan, Seaton, Rosen, & Tingley, 2017). The course-related factors include course design, level of difficulty, time and the price, whereas academic factors

contain the feedback and the encouragement that is received from the instructors (Aldowah, et al., 2020).

Qiu (2020) affirms that the low course completion rate in Udemy is not an indicator of failure, as 92% of the students who joined courses in Udemy mentioned that the MOOCs they enrolled in helped them achieve their goals. Not every student joins the course intending to take the whole course from A to Z. According to Qiu (2020), 30% of the enrollees were motivated to take a particular course in order to be able to build something (e.g., application or software), 25% joined some courses to learn for various exams (e.g., language exam), or to get help with career change, and 10% needed aid in setting up their businesses.

The Students of MOOCs

In an attempt to know more about the students participating in MOOCs, Christensen, Steinmetz, Alcorn, Bennett, Woods and Emanuel (2013) investigated Coursera, a MOOC platform, using an online survey. They identified the types of students enrolling in MOOCs and their reasons for registering. Approximately 35 thousand students participated in this survey, of which 79.4% hold bachelor's degrees or higher. Moreover, this study revealed that over 40% of the participants were less than 30 years old. Apart from being educated and young, the majority of MOOC students were males, employed, and from developed countries. In addition to identifying the characteristics of the students, the study also attempted to uncover their reasons for joining MOOCs. More than 90% of the students were motivated to participate in MOOCs for two main reasons: curiosity and gaining skills to boost their performance in their workplaces (Christensen, et al., 2013). While Christensen, et al.'s (2013) research seems to have yielded substantial results, it is unclear whether these results can be generalized to other MOOCs platforms such as Udemy.com, Edx.com, or udacity.com, since these platforms might provide different types of courses which may attract different types of participants with varying motivations. To further understand the motifs that encourage students to join MOOCs, Milligan and Littlejohn (2017) conducted an investigation to unravel the motivation to participate in Medical and Data science MOOCs. The results of the research suggest that the students took the courses to learn new skills, increase their efficiency at work, broaden their professional knowledge and to increase their chances of getting better positions or roles at work (Milligan & Littlejohn, 2017).

MOOCs can also be directly affiliated with universities, as seen in Mackness, et al.'s (2010) study on the participants in a MOOC set up by the University of Winnipeg. Similarly to Christenson et al. (2013), this study also offers insight into learners' perspectives on MOOCs, and reveals the appeal that these courses have for students. Participants in the study commented favorably on the autonomy which MOOCs allowed, as well as their openness, in terms of free enrollment and flexibility. Nonetheless, negative aspects were noted as well, such as a lack of interaction for some students as well as language issues for students from English as a foreign language (EFL) background (Mackness, et al., 2010).

Abeer's (2014) study shed light on the factors that impact the MOOC quality from the perspective of the enrollees. The study reported four main design features that determine the quality of MOOCs. They included visualizing the content, the instructor quality of explanation, the variety of assignments and the support that is received from the tutor (Abeer, 2014). Abeer's (2014) investigation concluded that students' competency and the design of the course are mutually dependent factors. That is, competent students tend not to complete an ill-designed MOOC while incompetent students left well-designed courses unfinished (Abeer, 2014).

The Instructors of MOOCs

Although instructors are usually authoritative figures in a particular field, it should be noted that almost anyone can design and teach a MOOC (Hoy, 2014). Rhodes (2015) differentiates between two types of MOOC instructors, namely, cMOOC and xMOOC instructors. In the case of cMOOC, the instructor is not the only source of knowledge, and the direction of the course is rather defined by the students (Rodriguez, 2012). With xMOOC, however, the tutors exercise more control (e.g., including and excluding material) over the content of the course (Rhodes, 2015). At the very beginning of MOOC movements in higher education, Allen and Seaman's (2014) investigation reported that 77% of their participants (instructors) said that they find MOOCs an inappropriate method for teaching due to the large number of students which may hinder the interaction between the teacher and the students. Evans and Myrick (2015) carried out a research study to measure the satisfaction of MOOC educators with MOOCs. Their results suggest that the more MOOCs the instructors teach the more satisfied they become. Also, when the participants were asked whether they would consider teaching a MOOC, only a fraction below 2% said they would not (Evans & Myrick, 2015). This may implicate that the negative preconceptions about the efficiency of MOOCs may dissuade the instructors from participating in MOOCs.

After investigating the existing body of literature on MOOCs, Hew and Cheung (2014) could identify three main types of motifs that drive instructors to create MOOCs. The first type reflects a desire to gain new experience from using the MOOC format, as designing a MOOC provides instructors with valuable experience in online education. The second reflects a desire for personal gain in terms of reputation or career goals. Lastly, instructors are also motivated by a sense of altruism, and see MOOCs as a means to help others by providing students worldwide with access to higher education (Hew & Chung, 2014, pp.49-50). However, Lowenthal, Snelson and Perkins (2018) believe that MOOC instructors are encouraged by intrinsic motivations more than extrinsic ones. This claim was also substantiated by Doo, Tang, Bonk and Zhu's (2020) study, which examined what motivated instructors to design MOOCs. The results showed that almost 87% of the motifs were intrinsic, such as serving the community, interest in modern learning technology and personal growth. About 13% percent of the instructors were motivated by extrinsic motifs, such as institutional goals, research purposes and financial gains.

MOOCs can also present challenges to instructors, who are not able to connect on a personal level with the thousands of students enrolled in their course as they would in a conventional classroom. This concern is reflected in the interviews with MOOC instructors conducted by Mackness, et al. (2010). Another concern that was expressed by several MOOC tutors was the long time that designing a MOOC demands (Doo, et al., 2020). Doo, et al.'s (2020) investigation included 142 MOOC instructors. They were also asked whether they received any type of training before designing their MOOCs. Surprisingly, only 13.38% of the participants reported that they had received professional training prior to designing their MOOCs. The rest, nonetheless, learned it by doing.

The Providers of MOOCs

According to Rhodes (2015), there is a difference between MOOC providers and MOOC producers in the sense that the latter includes those who design and teach MOOCs, while the former involves the organizations that support the development of MOOCs and facilitate access for the online learners. As the current dissertation investigates a go-profit platform (i.e., Udemy), the present section seeks to shine a light on go-profit platforms.

MOOC platforms seek to increase the number of enrollees by developing the quality and the interactivity of the courses provided (Conache, Dima, & Mutu, 2016). The most popular MOOC platforms in sequence are Coursera, EdX, Udacity, Udemy and Khan Academy (Conache, et al., 2016). According to Cetina, Goldbach and Manea (2018), Udemy offered 65,000 online courses on more than 142 topics, and these courses were taken by 20 million students. The students who enroll in Udemy MOOCs are from around 200 countries and one third of them are from the United States (Qiu, 2020). Szabó (2021) carried out an investigation into the Udemy Platform in order to reveal the most popular courses in Udemy and the number of enrollees. The most popular courses in Udemy are the programming language Python with almost 24 million students, web development (8 million), ethical hacking (7.7 million) and photoshop (8.3 million) among others (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Number of Participants in the Most Popular Topics of the Udemy Platform in 2020

Note. Adapted from “Online Platform Courses Between Education and Business” by E. Szabo, 2021, *Annals of Constantin Brancusi University of Targu-Jiu*, (1/2021), p. 202. Copyright 2021 by Academia Brâncuși Publisher.

Udemy platform is different from the rest of the go-profit platforms in the sense that they give the chance for anyone to produce and participate in the platform. Put simply, anyone can produce a MOOC, and anyone can participate in a MOOC in Udemy (Conache, et al., 2016). Not being supported by prestigious universities is a major drawback for the Udemy platform (Cetina, et al., 2018). Qiu (2020:2018) argues that Udemy is a sustainable “learning ecosystem” in the sense that besides being able to spread knowledge, the instructors of Udemy can also get paid for teaching, if they wish. The majority of the courses on Udemy are priced, but there is another platform called ‘Udemy Free Resource Center’ which provides free courses (Szabó, 2021). The prices of the Udemy MOOCs start from around 13 euro and vary according to the topic of the MOOC, for instance, the average price of a business course is 80 euro and the average price of a software development MOOC is 107 euro (Szabó, 2021).

Conache, et al. (2016) conducted a comparative study among EdX, Udacity, Udemy, and Coursera to provide a better understanding of the popularity, business model and course design of these platforms. The results (relevant to the current dissertation) of the study suggest that Udemy and Udacity are more focused on workforce training and increasing employability whereas Coursera and EdX are concerned with students and faculty. As for the course producers,

they range from individual tutors (especially Udemey) to corporations (especially Udacity), or universities (Especially EdX).

The possibility of introducing MOOCs to secondary education was explored by Politis, Koutsakas and Karagiannidis (2017). The authors used the Udemey platform to introduce a computer programming course for Greek secondary school students. The students' behavior was observed and they were asked to fill in questionnaires before and after taking the MOOC. The surveys sought to collect information about the students' expectations, experience, and the reason why they joined the course or left the course unfinished. The participants in the study reported an overall very favorable experience with the MOOC. The students expected MOOCs to have a positive influence on the educational process. They also mentioned that they were satisfied with the knowledge they gained from the attended MOOC (Politis, et al., 2017).

Summary

The aim of the current literature review was to provide an overview of Massive open Online courses to help understand this phenomenon. Insights about the development trajectory, the students, the tutors, and providers were given. The most significant findings of previous research that bear relevance to the current theoretical investigation can be summarized as follows:

- **MOOCs** are pre-recorded online courses that can be accessed or provided by anyone around the world.
- MOOC **proponents** saw an opportunity for a large number of people to have access to higher education while the opponents were either skeptical or saw it as another tool in the hand of the west to control higher education around the world.
- **Students** enroll in MOOCs in order to improve their professional knowledge, learn a new skill to advance at work, or out of curiosity. Studies reported that the autonomy which MOOCs provide and high-quality design of the courses were received positively by the students, while lack of interaction and low quality (design) courses were not.
- The **instructors** of MOOCs are motivated by the desire to achieve their career goals, help students gain experience, or by possible financial gains. The main challenges that MOOC instructors face are the lack of training and the fact that designing a MOOC is time-consuming.
- Some MOOC **platforms** provide courses for free (e.g., Coursera) while others offer paid courses besides the free ones (e.g., Udemey).

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